

Improved synthesis of natural ester sintenin and its analogues via Wittig reaction[†]

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Abstract : The synthesis of a cytotoxic natural ester sintenin (7a) and twenty eight of its analogues including nitrogen-containing heterocyclic indole moiety (7b-7t), saturated (10a-10d) and unsaturated (10e-10h) amides were carried out by convenient route via one-pot Wittig reaction in aqueous medium with improved yield. A systematic structure activity relationship of sintenin ester was designed by chemically modified derivatives in order to get better cytotoxicity.

Keywords : Natural ester, sintenin, Wittig reaction, cytotoxicity, SAR.

Introduction

Natural esters are known for their potent biological activities such as anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, anti-tumor, antioxidant, anti-HIV and lipid peroxidation¹. Isolation and cytotoxic evaluation of natural compounds has remained an area of active research for the search of new leads for antitumor drugs². In 2003, Chen and co-workers reported the isolation and cytotoxic activity of natural ester 3-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)propyl-3-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)propanoate (sintenin 7a), against P-388, HT-29 or A549 cell lines *in vitro*³. Sintenin has shown selective cytotoxicity with an ED₅₀ value of 5.4×10^{-7} M against P-388 cells. Zhou *et al.* have reported the cytotoxic activity of sintenin and its analogues against six human tumour cell lines such as PC-3, Hela, A549, BEL7404, CNE and KB⁴. However, the reported methods for the synthesis of sintenin and its derivatives suffer from drawbacks such as usage of toxic reagents (pyridine, piperidine, etc.) and required a large number of steps with poor overall yield (49%)^{3,4}.

As a part of our ongoing work towards the synthesis of biologically active compounds⁵ and interesting biological activity profile of natural esters prompted us to design a convenient route to synthesize natural ester sintenin and also its chemically modified derivatives in

order to get better cytotoxicity.

Results and discussion

In order to improve the yield, we designed an alternative route for the synthesis of sintenin and its derivatives. It mainly started from the one-pot Wittig reaction of aromatic and heterocyclic aldehydes with ethyl bromoacetate and Ph₃P in aqueous NaHCO₃ at room temperature, which gave unsaturated esters 2 with excellent yields in short reaction time⁶. The separate DIBAL-H reduction and base-catalysed hydrolysis of 2 gave the unsaturated alcohol 3 and carboxylic acid 4, respectively with good yield⁷. These were treated with hydrogen gas and Pd/C catalyst in MeOH solvent for overnight at room temperature to furnish saturated alcohol 3 and carboxylic acid 4, respectively with improved yield, as shown in Scheme 1.

The alcohol 5 and carboxylic acid 6 were subjected to carbonyldiimidazole (CDI) and 1,8-diazabicyclo-[5.4.0]undec-7-ene (DBU)-mediated coupling reaction to furnish natural ester sintenin and its analogues (Table 1, 7a-7t). The overall yield (85%) of sintenin improved approximately two fold than the reported methods in the literature⁴. Various analogues of sintenin were obtained from the coupling of substituted alcohols (5b-5t) with carboxylic acids (6b-6t) with the good yields 60-78% in 6 h, as shown in Table 1.

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Ar = 4-CH₃C₆H₄, 4-C₂H₅C₆H₄, 4-C₃H₇C₆H₄, 4-OMeC₆H₄, 3,4-OCH₃C₆H₄, 4-ClC₆H₄, 4-BrC₆H₄, Indolyl

Reagents and conditions : (i) Ethyl bromoacetate, Ph₃P, NaHCO₃ (aq.), rt, 2 h, 85–92%; (ii) DIBAL-H, dry CH₂Cl₂, 0 °C, rt, 3 h 80–90%; (iii) 1 M aq. KOH, THF, reflux, 1 h, 90–95%; (iv) H₂ balloon, 10% Pd/C, EtOAc, rt, 12 h, 90–96%

Scheme 1

Nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds, particularly 3-substituted indole moieties, are of much importance because they exist in many natural products. It is also considered as a potent pharmacophore and has a wide range of biological applications⁸. To make a systematic structure activity relationship of sintenin ester, we decided to incorporate indole moiety in the ester structure. The CDI-DBU-mediated coupling reaction of various alcohols bearing electron-withdrawing and electron-donating groups with indole containing carboxylic acid (7q-7t) gave moderate yields 50–55% as shown in Table 1.

In order to study the effect of amide linkage on biological activity of sintenin ester, we designed amide scaffold⁹ by replacing 3-phenylpropan-1-ol derivatives (5) with 3-phenylpropylamine (9). The coupling of amine (9) with unsaturated or saturated carboxylic acids (4 or 6) was achieved by reacting with ethyl chloroformate and triethylamine, which gave unsaturated (10a-10d) and satu-

Table 1. Synthesis of natural ester sintenin (7a) and its analogues (7b-7t)

Compound	Ar ^I	Ar ^{II}	Yield (%) ^a
7a	3,4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₃	3,4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₃	75
7b	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	68
7c	4-C ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	60
7d	4-C ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	72
7e	4-C ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	78
7f	4-C ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	75
7g	4- ⁱ prC ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	76
7h	4- ⁱ prC ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	78
7i	4- ⁱ prC ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	65
7j	4- ⁱ prC ₆ H ₄	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	70
7k	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	70
7l	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	66
7m	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	63
7n	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	65
7o	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	73
7p	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	68
7q	3-Indolyl	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55
7r	3-Indolyl	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	50
7s	3-Indolyl	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	53
7t	3-Indolyl	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	52

^aIsolated yields of pure products.

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR of natural ester sintenin 7a.

Fig. 2. ¹³C NMR of natural ester sintenin 7a.

rated (11a-11d) amides (Table 2).

Moreover, substrates having electron-donating or withdrawing groups led to the formation of amide products

and the reactions proceeded smoothly in short reaction time with yields in the range of 80–92%, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Synthesis of unsaturated and saturated amide derivatives of sintenin (10a-10d and 11a-11d)

where Ar¹ = Me, Et, ⁱpr, OMe, Cl

Compound ^a	Ar ¹	Yield (%) ^b
10a	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	80
10b	4-C ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	83
10c	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	88
10d	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	92
11a	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	80
11b	4-C ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	85
11c	4- ⁱ prC ₆ H ₄	82
11d	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	85

^a10a-10d : 2',3' is double bond and 11a-11d : 2',3' is saturated ethylene.^bIsolated yields of pure products.

Conclusion

We have succeeded in the synthesis of a cytotoxic natural ester sintenin (7a) and twenty eight of its analogues by convenient route via one-pot Wittig reaction in aqueous medium with improved yields. Moreover, the synthesis of amide analogues of sintenin natural product was achieved with excellent yields for the first time. The simplicity of the present synthetic route makes it an interesting alternative to other approaches.

Experimental

General procedure for the synthesis of sintenin ester derivatives (7a-7t) : To a stirred solution of carboxylic acid **6** (0.56 mmol) in dry THF (10 mL), CDI (8.42 mmol) in dry THF was added under nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was stirred at 45 °C for 15 min. The solution of alcohol **5** (0.56 mmol) and DBU (0.61 mmol) in dry THF (10 mL) was then added quickly to the above mixture. The resulting mixture was stirred at 45 °C for 6 h. After completion of the reaction (TLC), the excess solvent was evaporated to afford a residue, which was subjected to column chromatography to provide sintenin and its derivatives (7a-7t).

3-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)propyl-3-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)propanoate (7a) : Yield : 75%; colorless oil; ¹H

NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 6.78 (2H, d, *J* 8.05 Hz, Ar-H), 6.74 (2H, dd, *J* 8.0, 1.46 Hz, Ar-H), 6.69 (1H, dd, *J* 8.0, 1.46 Hz, Ar-H), 6.67 (1H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, Ar-H), 3.86, 3.85, 3.84 and 3.83 (3H each, s, 4 × OCH₃), 2.90 (2H, t, *J* 7.69 Hz), 2.62 and 2.57 (2H each, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 1.93–1.89 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : 30.2, 30.4, 31.5, 36.0, 55.6, 55.71, 55.75, 63.6, 77.2, 111.1, 111.4, 119.9, 120.0, 132.9, 133.5, 147.1, 147.3, 148.7, 172.8; ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 388.19 (M⁺). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₂H₂₈O₆ : C, 68.02; H, 7.27. Found : C, 68.05; H, 7.30.

3-p-Tolylpropionic acid 3-(4-chlorophenyl)propyl ester (7b) : Yield : 68%; yellow oil; IR (Film, cm⁻¹) : 2926, 2854, 1740, 1492, 1454, 1261, 1159, 1091, 1015; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 174–1.84 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.20 (3H, s, PhCH₃), 2.46–2.55 (4H, m, 2CH₂), 2.81 (2H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz, Ar-CH₂CH₂CO), 3.96 (2H, t, *J* 6.3 Hz, OCH₂CH₂), 6.94–7.01 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.12–7.16 (2H, m, Ar-H); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 316.52 (M⁺), 318.62 (M⁺+2). Anal. Calcd. for C₁₉H₂₁ClO₂ : C, 72.03; H, 6.68. Found : C, 72.05; H, 6.70.

3-(4-Ethylphenyl)propionic acid 3-(4-chlorophenyl)propyl ester (7c) : Yield : 60%; pale yellow liquid; IR (Film cm⁻¹) : 2962, 2927, 2856, 1735, 1515, 1493, 1453, 1158, 1091, 1015; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.20

(3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 1.84–1.93 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.56–2.64 (6H, m, 3CH₂), 2.92 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, Ar-CH₂CH₂CO), 4.06 (2H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz, OCH₂CH₂), 7.05–7.14 (6H, m), 7.22–7.25 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : 14.5, 27.3, 28.6, 29.5, 30.2, 34.8, 62.4, 126.9, 127.3, 127.3, 127.4, 128.6, 130.6, 136.5, 141.1, 171.9; ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 330.26 (M⁺), 332.52 (M⁺+2). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₃ClO₂ : C, 72.61; H, 7.01. Found : C, 72.65; H, 7.06.

3-(4-Ethylphenyl)propionic acid 3-(4-bromophenyl)propyl ester (7d) : Yield : 72%; pale yellow oil; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.13 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 1.79–1.84 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.48–2.57 (6H, m, 3CH₂), 2.84 (2H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz, Ar-CH₂CH₂CO), 3.99 (2H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz, OCH₂CH₂), 7.05–7.14 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.22–7.25 (2H, m, Ar-H); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 374.5249 (M⁺), 376.1547 (M⁺+2). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₃BrO₂ : C, 64.01; H, 6.18. Found : C, 64.06; H, 6.20.

3-(4-Ethylphenyl)propionic acid 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)propyl ester (7e) : Yield : 78%; yellow oil; IR (Film, cm⁻¹) : 2927, 2863, 1734, 1613, 1513, 1457, 1246, 1174, 1037; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.20 (3H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 1.83–1.93 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.54–2.64 (6H, m, 3CH₂), 2.91 (2H, t, *J* 8.1 Hz, Ar-CH₂CH₂CO), 3.77 (3H, s, PhOCH₃), 4.06 (2H, t, *J* 8.4 Hz, OCH₂CH₂), 6.80–6.83 (2H, m), 7.04–7.23 (6H, m); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 326.3428 (M⁺). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₆O₃ : C, 77.27; H, 8.03. Found : C, 77.30; H, 8.06.

3-(4-Ethylphenyl)propionic acid 3-p-tolylpropyl ester (7f) : Yield : 75%; brown oil; IR (Film, cm⁻¹) : 3018, 2962, 2928, 2852, 1738, 1515, 1452, 805; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.20 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 1.88–1.93 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.31 (3H, s, PhCH₃), 2.57–2.62 (6H, m, 3CH₂), 2.91 (2H, t, *J* 8.0 Hz, Ar-CH₂CH₂CO), 4.07 (2H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz, OCH₂CH₂), 7.03–7.12 (8H, m); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 1310.2547 (M⁺). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₆O₂ : C, 81.25; H, 8.44. Found : C, 81.28; H, 8.47.

3-(4-i-Propylphenyl)propionic acid 3-(4-chlorophenyl)propyl ester (7g) : Yield : 76%; yellow oil; IR (Film, cm⁻¹) : 2959, 2927, 2869, 1735, 1514, 1492, 1458, 1262, 1160, 1092; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.14 (6H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz, CH(CH₃)₂), 1.79–1.87 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂),

2.49–2.58 (4H, m, 2CH₂), 2.76–2.87 (3H, m), 3.99 (2H, t, *J* 6.3 Hz, OCH₂CH₂), 6.98–7.04 (2H, m), 7.06–7.14 (4H, m), 7.17–7.22 (2H, m); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 344.9214 (M⁺), 346.6247 (M+2). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₅ClO₂ : C, 73.14; H, 7.31. Found : C, 73.10; H, 7.40.

3-(4-i-Propylphenyl)propionic acid 3-(4-bromophenyl)propyl ester (7h) : Yield : 78%; pale yellow oil; IR (Film, cm⁻¹) : 2959, 2924, 2852, 1737, 1488, 1259, 1159, 1011, 824; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.21 (6H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz, CH(CH₃)₂), 1.87–1.93 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.56–2.64 (4H, m, 2CH₂), 2.85–2.94 (3H, m), 4.07 (2H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz, OCH₂CH₂), 7.01 (2H, d, *J* 9.2 Hz), 7.14 (4H, s), 7.38 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 388.4167 (M⁺), 390.4524 (M+2). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₅BrO₂ : C, 64.78; H, 6.47. Found : C, 64.78; H, 6.47.

3-(4-i-Propylphenyl)propionic acid 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)propyl ester (7i) : Yield : 65%; brown oil; IR (Film, cm⁻¹) : 2958, 2927, 2863, 1735, 1612, 1513, 1513, 1464, 1246; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.21 (6H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz, CH(CH₃)₂), 1.84–1.93 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.55–2.64 (4H, m, 2CH₂), 2.82–2.95 (3H, m), 3.78 (3H, s, PhOCH₃), 4.07 (2H, t, *J* 6.3 Hz, OCH₂CH₂), 6.80–6.83 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.05–7.14 (6H, m, Ar-H); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 340.8436 (M⁺). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₂H₂₈O₃ : C, 77.61; H, 8.29. Found : C, 77.59; H, 8.30.

3-(4-i-Propylphenyl)propionic acid 3-p-tolylpropyl ester (7j) : Yield : 70%; yellow oil; IR (Film, cm⁻¹) : 2959, 2926, 1735, 1515, 1458, 1361, 1289, 1260, 1159; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.11 (6H, d, *J* 5.1 Hz, CH(CH₃)₂), 1.76–1.85 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.21 (3H, s, PhCH₃), 2.47–2.55 (4H, m, 2CH₂), 2.72–2.85 (3H, m), 4.00 (2H, t, *J* 6.3 Hz, OCH₂CH₂), 6.93–7.16 (8H, m, Ar-H); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 324.6272 (M⁺). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₂H₂₈O₂ : C, 81.44; H, 8.70. Found : C, 81.48; H, 8.52.

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)propionic acid 3-(4-chlorophenyl)propyl ester (7k) : Yield : 70%; yellow oil; IR (Film, cm⁻¹) : 2922, 2851, 1735, 1512, 1246, 1176, 1035, 824; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.84–1.93 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.59 (4H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz, 2CH₂), 2.89 (2H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz, Ar-CH₂CH₂CO), 3.77 (3H, s, PhOCH₃), 4.06 (2H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz, OCH₂CH₂), 6.81 (2H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz), 7.05–7.13 (4H, m), 7.22–7.26 (2H, m); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 316.6217 (M⁺), 318.2632 (M⁺+2). Anal. Calcd.

for $C_{19}H_{21}ClO_3$: C, 68.57; H, 6.36. Found : C, 68.55; H, 6.40.

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)propionic acid 3-(4-bromophenyl)propyl ester (7l) : Yield : 66%; yellow oil; IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 2954, 2861, 1733, 1612, 1513, 1488, 1247, 1177, 1011, 827; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.88–1.97 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.54–2.63 (4H, m, $2CH_2$), 2.89 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, Ar- CH_2CH_2CO), 3.78 (3H, s, $PhOCH_3$), 4.06 (2H, t, J 6.3 Hz, OCH_2CH_2), 6.81 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 6.99 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.10 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.37 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz); ESI-MS (m/z) : 376.2469 (M^+), 378.4419 ($M^+ + 2$). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{21}BrO_3$: C, 60.49; H, 5.61. Found : C, 60.52; H, 5.63.

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)propionic acid 3-p-tolylpropyl ester (7m) : Yield : 63%; yellow oil; IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 2924, 2853, 1735, 1611, 1513, 1247, 1177, 1036, 825; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.85–1.94 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.31 (3H, s, $PhCH_3$), 2.59 (4H, t, J 7.5 Hz, $2CH_2$), 2.89 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, Ar- CH_2CH_2CO), 3.77 (3H, s, $PhOCH_3$), 4.07 (2H, t, J 6.3 Hz, OCH_2CH_2), 6.81 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.02–7.13 (6H, m, Ar-H); ESI-MS (m/z) : 312.2629 (M^+). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{24}O_3$: C, 76.89; H, 7.74. Found : C, 76.92; H, 7.78.

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)propionic acid 3-(4-chlorophenyl)propyl ester (7n) : Yield : 65%; yellow oil; IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 2922, 2852, 1735, 1493, 1092, 1015, 818; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.87–1.92 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.57–2.62 (4H, m, $2CH_2$), 2.91 (2H, t, J 7.6 Hz, Ar- CH_2CH_2CO), 4.06 (2H, t, J 6.4 Hz, OCH_2CH_2), 7.05 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.12 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.23–7.26 (4H, m, Ar-H); ESI-MS (m/z) : 336.9653 (M^+), 338.4418 ($M^+ + 2$), 340.7216 ($M^+ + 4$). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{18}Cl_2O_2$: C, 64.11; H, 5.38. Found : C, 64.11; H, 5.38.

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)propionic acid 3-(4-bromophenyl)propyl ester (7o) : Yield : 73%; yellow oil; IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3028, 2956, 2857, 1734, 1653, 1260, 1161, 818, 700; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.76–1.85 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.47–2.55 (4H, m, $2CH_2$), 2.83 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, Ar- CH_2CH_2CO), 3.98 (2H, t, J 6.3 Hz, OCH_2CH_2), 6.92 (2H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.04 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 7.16 (2H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 7.30 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz); ESI-MS (m/z) : 380.8252 (M^+), 382.6147 ($M^+ + 2$), 384.1652 ($M^+ + 4$). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{18}BrClO_2$: C, 56.64; H,

4.75. Found : C, 56.68; H, 4.63.

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)propionic acid 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)propyl ester (7p) : Yield : 68%; yellow oil; IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 2922, 2851, 1735, 1512, 1246, 1176, 1035, 824; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.86–1.90 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.55–2.62 (4H, m, $2CH_2$), 2.91 (2H, t, J 8.0 Hz, Ar- CH_2CH_2CO), 3.78 (3H, s, $PhOCH_3$), 4.06 (2H, t, J 6.4 Hz, OCH_2CH_2), 6.81 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.04 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.13 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.24 (2H, d, J 6.8 Hz); ESI-MS (m/z) : 332.2471 (M^+), 334.5216 ($M^+ + 2$). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{21}ClO_3$: C, 68.57; H, 6.36. Found : C, 68.59; H, 6.38.

3-(1H-Indol-3-yl)propionic acid 3-p-tolylpropyl ester (7q) : Yield : 55%; brown oil; IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3413, 2922, 2852, 1719, 1456, 1259, 1160, 1068, 804, 740; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.86–1.93 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.31 (3H, s, $PhCH_3$), 2.58 (2H, t, J 8.8 Hz, CH_2CH_2CO), 2.73 (2H, t, J 9.2 Hz, CH_2CH_2Ph), 3.11 (2H, t, J 8.0 Hz, CH_2CH_2CO), 4.08 (2H, t, J 7.2 Hz, OCH_2CH_2), 7.02–7.22 (7H, m), 7.35 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.60 (1H, d, J 7.2 Hz), 7.95 (1H, s, NH); ESI-MS (m/z) : 321.5841 (M^+). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{23}NO_2$: C, 78.47; H, 7.21; N, 4.36. Found : C, 78.50; H, 7.23; N, 4.35.

3-(1H-Indol-3-yl)propionic acid 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)propyl ester (7r) : Yield : 50%; brown oil; IR (Film cm^{-1}) : 3413, 2928, 2854, 1725, 1611, 1512, 1458, 1340, 1245; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.85–1.92 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.57 (2H, t, J 10.4 Hz, CH_2CH_2CO), 2.73 (2H, t, J 8.0 Hz, CH_2CH_2Ph), 3.12 (2H, t, J 8.0 Hz, Ar- CH_2CH_2CO), 3.78 (3H, s, $PhOCH_3$), 4.07 (2H, t, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_2), 6.80 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.02–7.22 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.34 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.61–7.70 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.96 (1H, s, NH); ESI-MS (m/z) : 337.6941 (M^+). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{23}NO_3$: C, 74.75; H, 6.87; N, 4.15. Found : C, 74.78; H, 6.85; N, 4.12.

3-(1H-Indol-3-yl)propionic acid 3-(4-chlorophenyl)propyl ester (7s) : Yield : 53%; brown oil; IR (Film, cm^{-1}) : 3411, 2926, 2852, 1708, 1647, 1491, 1458, 1340, 1159; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.84–1.91 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.56 (2H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH_2CH_2CO), 2.73 (2H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH_2CH_2Ph), 3.11 (2H, t, J 8.4 Hz, CH_2CH_2CO), 4.08 (2H, t, J 8.4 Hz, OCH_2CH_2), 7.02–7.23 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.35 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.60

(1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 8.07 (1H, s, NH); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 341.6341 (M⁺), 343.3158 (M⁺+2). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₀ClNO₂ : C, 70.27; H, 5.90; N, 4.10. Found : C, 70.30; H, 5.87; N, 4.08.

3-(1H-Indol-3-yl)propionic acid 3-(4-bromophenyl)-propyl ester (7t) : Yield : 52%; brown oil; IR (Film cm⁻¹) : 3411, 2924, 1719, 1458, 1340, 1159, 1071, 1010, 741; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 186–1.89 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.54 (2H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz, CH₂CH₂CO), 2.73 (2H, t, *J* 8.0 Hz, Ar-CH₂CH₂Ph), 3.12 (2H, t, *J* 11.2 Hz, CH₂CH₂CO), 4.07 (2H, t, *J* 8.0 Hz, OCH₂CH₂), 6.96–7.02 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.11–7.22 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.35–7.38 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.60 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.96 (1H, s, NH); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 385.2927 (M⁺), 387.1628 (M⁺+2). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₀BrNO₂ : C, 62.19; H, 5.22; N, 3.63. Found : C, 62.23; H, 5.25; N, 3.68.

General procedure for the synthesis of saturated and unsaturated amide derivatives (10a-10h) : To a solution of unsaturated or saturated carboxylic acid (**4** or **6**) (1.23 mmol) in dry THF, triethylamine (1.85 mmol) and ethylchloroformate (1.35 mmol) was added and stirred for 30 min at room temperature, and primary amine **9** (1.23 mmol) was added to this reaction mixture and stirred for 60 min. After completion of the reaction (TLC), the reaction mixture was washed with cold 1 *N* HCl and extracted with chloroform. The organic extract was washed with brine, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure to afford a solid compounds (**10a-10d**) and (**11a-11d**).

N-(3-Phenylpropyl)-3-p-tolylacrylamide (10a) : Yield : 80%; m.p. 98–100 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3247, 3030, 3061, 2958, 2844, 1654, 1514, 1541, 1340, 1232, 983, 816, 746, 696; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.86–1.96 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.36 (3H, s, PhCH₃), 2.69 (2H, t, *J* 9.0 Hz, CH₂CH₂Ph), 2.39–2.46 (2H, m, NHCH₂CH₂), 5.62 (1H, s, NH), 6.26 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 7.15–7.39 (9H, m, Ar-H), 7.55 (1H, d, *J* 15.0 Hz); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 279.2569 (M⁺). Anal. Calcd. for C₁₉H₂₁NO : C, 81.68; H, 7.58; N, 5.01. Found : C, 81.70; H, 7.55; N, 5.05.

3-(4-Ethylphenyl)-N-(3-phenylpropyl)acrylamide (10b) : Yield : 83%; m.p. 95–96 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3263, 2922, 2854, 1654, 1617, 1534, 1459, 1377, 1382,

1228; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.23 (3H, t, *J* 8.0 Hz, PhCH₂CH₂), 1.87–1.94 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.61–2.71 (4H, m), 3.39–3.44 (2H, m, NHCH₂CH₂), 5.78 (1H, s, NH), 6.29 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 7.17–7.30 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.39 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.55 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 293.6348 (M⁺). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₃NO : C, 81.87; H, 7.90; N, 4.77. Found : C, 81.90; H, 7.88; N, 4.75.

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-N-(3-phenylpropyl)acrylamide (10c) : Yield : 88%; m.p. 106–107 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3247, 2924, 2854, 1654, 1611, 1542, 1459, 1377, 1339, 1228; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.75–1.96 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.70 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH₂CH₂Ph), 3.39–3.46 (2H, m, NHCH₂CH₂), 5.62 (1H, s, NH), 6.26 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 7.18–7.42 (9H, m, Ar-H), 7.51 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 299.3468 (M⁺), 301.2414 (M⁺+2). Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₈ClNO : C, 72.11; H, 6.05; N, 4.67. Found : C, 72.15; H, 6.02; N, 4.63.

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-N-(3-phenylpropyl)acrylamide (10d) : Yield : 90%; m.p. 110–115 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3273, 2927, 2852, 1684, 1651, 1601, 1509, 1250, 1175, 828; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.86–1.95 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.69 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH₂CH₂Ph), 2.39–2.46 (2H, m, NHCH₂CH₂), 3.82 (3H, s, PhOCH₃), 5.61 (1H, s, NH), 6.18 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 7.18–7.31 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.42–7.58 (4H, m, Ar-H); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 295.3527 (M⁺). Anal. Calcd. for C₁₉H₂₁NO₂ : C, 77.26; H, 7.17; N, 4.74. Found : C, 77.28; H, 7.13; N, 4.72.

N-(3-Phenylpropyl)-3-p-tolylpropionamide (11a) : Yield : 80%; m.p. 84–85 °C; IR (KBr cm⁻¹) : 3311, 3060, 2927, 2872, 1642, 1540, 1452, 1233, 730, 696; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.70–1.80 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.29 (3H, s, PhCH₃), 2.40 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, NHCOCH₂), 2.55 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH₂CH₂CH₂NH), 2.89 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, COCH₂CH₂), 3.21–3.27 (2H, m, NHCH₂CH₂), 5.29 (1H, s, NH), 7.08–7.20 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.25–7.30 (2H, m, Ar-H); ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 281.3878 (M⁺). Anal. Calcd. for C₁₉H₂₃NO : C, 81.10; H, 8.24; N, 4.98. Found : C, 81.13; H, 8.26; N, 4.96.

3-(4-Ethylphenyl)-N-(3-phenylpropyl)propionamide (11b) : Yield : 85%; m.p. 65–66 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3312, 2928, 2873, 1642, 1541, 1452, 1233, 827, 730, 696; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.19 (3H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, PhCH₂CH₂), 1.70–1.80 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.40

(2H, t, J 7.2 Hz, NHCOCH_2), 2.53–2.66 (4H, m), 2.90 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, COCH_2CH_2), 3.21–3.28 (2H, m, NHCH_2CH_2), 5.27 (1H, s), 7.11–7.20 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.27–7.30 (2H, m, Ar-H); ESI-MS (m/z): 295.5741 (M^+). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{25}\text{NO}$: C, 81.31; H, 8.53; N, 4.74. Found: C, 81.35; H, 8.57; N, 4.71.

3-(4-Propylphenyl)-N-(3-phenylpropyl)propionamide (**11c**): Yield: 82%; IR (Film, cm^{-1}): 3293, 3025, 2959, 2928, 2868, 1644, 1552, 1453, 823, 699; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.12 (6H, d, J 6.9 Hz, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.62–1.72 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2$), 2.33 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, NHCOCH_2), 2.48 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}$), 2.72–2.84 (3H, m), 3.12–3.19 (2H, m, NHCH_2CH_2), 5.32 (1H, s), 7.01–7.12 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.16–7.21 (2H, m, Ar-H); ESI-MS (m/z): 309.9573 (M^+). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{27}\text{NO}$: C, 81.51; H, 8.79; N, 4.53. Found: C, 81.55; H, 8.80; N, 4.57.

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-N-(3-phenylpropyl)-propionamide (**11d**): Yield: 85%; m.p. 115–118 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3308, 3030, 2938, 2834, 1729, 1539, 1513, 1250, 1036, 698; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.70–1.80 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2$), 2.39 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, NHCOCH_2), 2.55 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}$), 2.88 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, COCH_2CH_2), 3.21–3.27 (2H, m, NHCH_2CH_2), 3.74 (3H, s, PhOCH_3), 5.28 (1H, s, NH), 6.80–6.82 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.09–7.20 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.25–7.30 (2H, m, Ar-H); ESI-MS (m/z): 297.2648 (M^+). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_2$: C, 76.73; H, 7.80; N, 4.71. Found: C, 76.76; H, 7.83; N, 4.74.

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